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Psychological Effects of Music Therapy On Teenagers in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

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APPROVAL SHEET

This undergraduate thesis entitled **“PSYCHOLOGICAL EFFECTS OF MUSIC THERAPY ON TEENAGERS IN KINGDOM OF SAUDI ARABIA,”** prepared and submitted by **IYAS NASSER** in partial fulfillment of the requirements for completion of **SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL** has been examined and is recommended for **ORAL EXAMINATION.**

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Abstract

Music has been used for centuries as a well-known therapy used on human beings on a wide range. For several years, nurses have utilized music as an intervention. Nurses and other health professionals have conducted a substantial number of studies to ascertain the effectiveness of music in managing pain, reducing anxiety and aggressive behaviors, and increasing performance and well-being. The researchers analyzed study publications on nursing and unrelated topics that were published between 1980 and 1997. There was a lot of difference in the demographics investigated, the methodology employed, the type of musical selection used, and the dose of the intervention (number of sessions and length of exposure). Overall, it was discovered that music is beneficial in bringing about favorable results. Based on the patients' training and education, music therapists apply several theoretical viewpoints. Numerous philosophies, such as humanism, cognitive-behavioral theory, and existentialism, have an impact on clinical practice. Music has been proven to be effective in curing, healing, and interacting with the psychological state of someone's life. After World War I and World War II, community musicians of all stripes, both amateur and professional, visited veterans' hospitals across the nation to perform for the thousands of soldiers suffering from both physical and psychological wounds caused by the wars. This is when music therapy as it is currently understood today first emerged.

CHAPTER I

The Problem

Introduction

It can be enjoyable to listen to music, and some study even suggests that it might improve your health. There are numerous other psychological advantages to listening to music in addition to the potential for enjoyment and fulfillment. Music has the power to uplift the spirit, revitalize the body, and even improve pain management.

In this study, the researcher intends to raise awareness; furthermore, educate the readers on how music is a well-proven therapy that is not as well-known as the other therapeutic lines. This therapy is one of the most effective and less time-consuming which is related to how it noticeably affects the patient's psychological state. To enhance a client's health and well-being, music therapy uses methods like listening to, reflecting on, and making music. People can more readily express themselves, recognize and process challenging events, improve their social and communication skills, or just find emotional relief by being exposed to music. The therapy can take place in a group or individual setting and is directed by a board-certified music therapist. It is frequently used in conjunction with other treatments or drugs. To create a plan to treat the patient's condition, a musical

therapist must first, assess the patient's condition and talk to them about their musical preferences. The therapist chooses the instrument or instruments to be utilized in therapy as well as the musical style after consulting with the patient. The AMTA reports that the early 1900s saw a rise in interest in the therapeutic effects of music; the first academic program in music therapy was created at Michigan State University in 1944, and the field of study as a whole was born. University of Kansas, College of the Pacific, Averno College, and Chicago Musical College are other "pioneers" that offer music therapy courses.

Background of the study

The researcher chose to conduct this study in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, in Riyadh. As well as that, this psychiatrist, who will help us learn more about this subject, will also be in the Kingdom. This is for other reasons, such as increasing awareness of music in the Arab Kingdom. Saudi Arabia and let everyone know the extent of its impact on the inner mind and the daily behavior of a person, especially adolescents. This is this goal, to educate all those interested in the subject, and even the ones who are not interested, to give the subject the attention it deserves, and to be proud of the extent to which most of the population in Saudi Arabia, especially in Riyadh, has come to know the importance of the

impact music has on the human mind. In this study, the researchers target adolescents from the age of 13 to 19, because the researchers know what music changes in them. Every day, teenage children face feelings of shame, jealousy, and guilt. It is natural for their moods to fluctuate sharply as a result of the conflicting emotions. Music helps train a teenager to control his emotions. It also allows them to express themselves. It helps reduce sick anxiety and improve the ability to focus. This helps in adopting music in treating psychological disorders in teens, as music therapy can reduce depression and increase self-confidence in adolescents, who are exposed at this stage of life to many pitfalls and challenges that cause them emotional disorders and behavioral problems. Music therapy improves the adolescent's self-image and improves communication. It can also mitigate severe, harsh, and maladaptive behaviors in adolescents, and increase interaction in the community. Music also helps teens increase their ability to be independent, self-directed, creative, and imaginative.

Music therapy has become a form of complementary or even alternative medicine, as music has contributed to restoring and improving the health, psychological, physical, physiological, and spiritual conditions of many patients who suffer from problems of different natures and causes. It has been scientifically proven that the vibrations of music directly affect the nervous system, as each vibration or more affects a part of the brain, specific to a nerve, which contributes

to allowing the listener to relax, which is what scientists liken to the process of medical anesthesia, and this condition allows for relaxation. The will to overcome the causes of pain, so the body begins to activate natural antibodies and internal secretions that help the immune system and others to overcome the source and location of the disease. Music therapy Noise has become a distinctive feature of modern life, and modern science confirms that it causes many health risks in humans, such as high blood pressure, tachycardia, and other physical and psychological health problems. In this context, a logical question arises. If there are disturbing sounds that cause disease, aren't there sounds that help heal, and can sounds, tones, and rhythms be a substitute for medicine or a complement to it? And can music be a treatment that goes hand in hand with a pill? History of music therapy: Music therapy has been known since ancient times, as the primitive man used to sing and dance as part of his rituals to expel evil spirits that were believed to be behind many diseases, and the priests of the Abydos Temple, the largest medical center in Pharaonic Egypt, used to treat diseases with melodious chanting. Plato confirms in the fourth book of the Republic that access to health is achieved through music and gymnastics, and there is an old papyrus indicating that there is a saint named Abu Tarbo who used to treat epilepsy patients in the Coptic era by reciting psalms. Also, the philosopher and mathematician

«Pythagoras» began 2500 years ago to teach his students that sounds help work, relax, sleep, and wake up well.

In the modern era, the history of using music as a therapeutic method date back to 1896, when modern medical interest in the positive effect of music began in the United States and that it increases blood flow and helps mental clarity, this history can be adopted as the beginning of the attention of modern medicine to sound therapy and music therapy. In the fifties and sixties of the twentieth century, electronic devices were developed that emit sound waves for treatment and others for diagnosis. The British doctor, Peter Manners, devised a device that emits sound waves for topical treatment. French otologists Guy Berard and Ecfried Tomati invented the method of integrative auditory training using devices that emit sounds with selected waves to train autistic and stuttering children to hear and perceive sounds that were difficult for them to communicate with. In the last decade of the twentieth century, Finnish doctors developed a way to use sound waves that can prevent complications from heart and arterial diseases by lowering high blood pressure and relieving muscle tension.

Statement of the problem

The problem the researcher faced in this study is that the society in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia underestimates the idea that music therapy can help teenagers overcome their mental illness.

Society takes teenagers' mental health as something not serious and not real, and they take music therapy as a silly myth that doesn't affect teenagers in any way, they are also taking it as a joke and a really big part of society thinks that its Superstitions from the therapists so that they can take money for their benefits. In this study, the researcher will raise awareness about music therapy and its psychological effects and how it determines teens' psychological state. The researchers will mainly focus on teens in this study; furthermore, educate readers in this area. Music therapy is still highly underestimated as a result: in this study, the researchers will try out these best powers to not only prove but educate and spread how music therapy affects teens and their mental state. With the help of previous studies and a wide range of globally known psychiatrists, The researchers' study will indicate music therapy worth.

Operational framework

Music can be used as a form of therapy, especially for adolescents. Music therapy includes age-appropriate music to support the diverse cognitive, physical,

psychological, and social needs of children and adolescents to help them reach their full potential.

According to the health site, therapy helps teens identify their strengths and serves as a means of self-expression and open communication. It is also commonly used to enhance the family bond between children and parents. Music has many important points that must be focused on, such as how it works, what it treats what is its effectiveness, and does it work for those who need it.

How does music therapy work?

The music therapist carefully analyzes the patient and tailors the treatment program according to the teen's individual needs. The therapist will start singing and playing instruments and encourage the patient to explore different instruments as well.

Then they document teenagers' development and evaluate sessions to track the child's progress. Contrary to popular belief, there is no need for musical experience to get music therapy.

Types of music therapy

Music therapy used with teens can be divided into two categories:

Recorded music: Refers to playing pre-recorded music or sounds through a phone or TV.

Live music is music or sounds that are sung or played in the present moment.

Develop sensory skills:

Sensory skills refer to the skills responsible for receiving information such as vision, hearing, touch, smell, and taste. Parents who sing to their babies while they are holding them develop a bond through skin-to-skin contact. Moreover, music therapy also helps adolescents build noise tolerance, allowing them to block out unnecessary noise and release stress.

Evolution of feeding habits:

Teenagers who receive recorded music therapy are more likely to have better feeding behavior. Since they can eat more food, the average daily weight of these children is also higher.

Speech and language:

Music therapy stimulates teens to interact, engage, and participate in a social setting. They also have better communication with their parents because music helps premature babies feel close to them.

Attention control:

Music therapy improves teenager's cognitive abilities, they have a longer attention span and stronger willpower to control emotions and behaviors.

Health improvement:

As their sensory habits, communication, feeding, and cognitive abilities improve, teens are likely to experience a decrease in stress and pain. Therefore, these teenagers tend to have healthier sleep patterns and normal breathing.

In addition, Therapy using music is one of the most important types of treatments used, which has proven to have good effects in treating some health and psychological problems such as dementia, depression, and many diseases that affect a person's mental health as a result of the pressures of life. Hearing some music during the hours of your day of different types may be able to change your condition. Psychological, which has a clear impact on physical and psychological health. Music is a powerful thing that may prompt researchers and doctors to use it as a treatment method that has great effectiveness. This is called "music therapy". During the sessions, the music therapist tries to form a bond with his clients to improve confidence, communication skills, awareness, and attention.

Because music can evoke positive feelings and stimulate the brain's reward centers, music therapy is often able to relieve symptoms of mental health problems

such as depression. Mood-related problems. Anxiety. Schizophrenia. Dependence on certain drugs. Autism personality disorders Insomnia. Dementia.

Music therapy is useful in treating adolescents who suffer from some psychological or mental problems, developmental or learning disabilities, other problems, and problems resulting from a person's exposure to aggression in one way or another, and in cases of brain injuries, physical disabilities, and acute and chronic pain.

The main goal of music therapy: Music plays a fundamental role in this identity, culture, heritage, and spiritual beliefs. It is a powerful medium that can affect us all deeply. Music therapy is used alongside traditional therapies, positive psychology, and even as a standalone intervention. The main goal of music therapy is to achieve goals that meet the needs of the individual. This may include, for example, improving motor function, social skills, emotions, coordination, self-expression, and personal growth.

Goals of music therapy for teens: Communication skills through the use of vocal and verbal sounds and gestures. Social skills include eye contact, taking turns, initiating interaction, and self-esteem. Sensory skills through touch, listening, and awareness levels. Physical skills include fine and gross movement control and

movement. Cognitive skills include focus, attention, imitation, and sequencing. Emotional skills include expressing feelings non-verbally.

Objectives

The objectives of this study is to help the study to educate parents about music therapy and how it can affect their teens and improve their mental health. A lot of parents have a lack of knowledge about the teenagers' emotions and feelings and they don't believe the facts that these therapies exist and can have a real effect on their health.

Raise awareness in the community toward the psychological effects of music on teens. Not only parents but the community as a whole doesn't believe that teenager's emotions are a real problem that teenagers can face. Music therapy is a real therapy that is studied by different people and can help teenagers. Introduce the advantages and disadvantages and the positive and negative effects of music on teenagers.

In this study, the researcher will introduce the advantages and disadvantages of music therapy and its effects whether it's negative or positive. Help teenagers understand how to deal with their emotions, feelings, or moods using music.

Teenagers do not know much about music therapy and don't know how to deal with their emotions. In this study, the researcher will try to show teenagers the right way to deal with all their emotions using music. Help teenagers express their emotions in the right way. Teenagers don't know how to express their emotions the right way so they start expressing their bad emotions and bad feelings through some bad habits that harm them or the people around them example: bullying, self-harm, substance use, etc.

Another aim of this study is to show teenagers the right way to express their feelings. Help teens in Saudi Arabia to improve self-esteem and self-expression. Teenagers in Saudi Arabia have a lack of expression and a lack of showing their feelings to others, especially their parents. In this study, researchers are trying to improve teenagers' self-esteem and self-expression.

Assumptions

In this step, the researcher goal is to evaluate the effects of music and how it impacts the working of the human brain. By doing so, the researcher with the assistance of the professionals will conclude the results. A set of a questionnaire is given to the participant. The participant reads it thoroughly and then answers the questions. Each respondent answers the questions based on their experiences.

Scope of the study

The study claims to be well-informed. This will state advantages and disadvantages however emotional connections and effects on emotions is an aspect that will not be included in this study.

Additionally, this psychiatrist, who will assist us in learning more about this subject, will be there as well. Another reason for this is to raise awareness of music in the Arab Kingdom.

Key points of this study

Music is a creative art form that allows emotions to be expressed and shared. In music therapy, teens can gain self-understanding and learn better ways to cope with their lives.

- Music therapy uses music and songs as therapeutic tools to help teens heal by encouraging self-expression and self-awareness.
- Living with Harmony music therapists are trained to help a teen deal with troubling problems or behaviors through the use of music.

Music is used in various ways. Sometimes teens want to compose their songs, listen to specific songs, or talk about how certain music changes their mood. Some teens find dance and movement freeing and pleasurable.

- Teens often discover that the words in popular songs express their feelings and experiences that they cannot express themselves.
- Teens tend to gravitate to music that describes what they are feeling and what is meaningful to them.

As part of this study, the researcher aims to create another world using music to take you into a comfortable atmosphere that makes you forget about your tiredness and constant anxiety. The researcher also aims to spread the meaning of music more and more so that everyone around us knows that the researcher wants to educate them about various topics that are unknown to them as teenagers and because they are immature. Their knowledge of all these details is rare as the researcher will feel proud when untreated individuals know that some people benefit from this study they may apply these treatments themselves, and it may also help them overcome difficult periods and make them more confident of themselves, serious and more mature, the researcher will feel that his efforts have had many benefits and have helped many adolescents.

Benefits of music therapy

As evidenced by the experiences of many people with music therapy after its recent spread and the positive results they found, this therapy has proven very beneficial, and among its most common benefits are: Music has a profound effect on memory: Improving memory and making it stronger is one of the most significant benefits of music therapy. When the researcher listens to a specific song, The researcher can remember events that occurred before when hearing the same music or things similar to it. Therefore, Alzheimer's treatment specialists listen to some songs for the elderly. Music attracts attention and focus: One can get another's attention through music and using musical compositions to catch the attention of someone while having fun. Music has a very big impact on emotions: Music helps us change the emotional state the researchers live in from sadness to happiness. There are types of songs that make us smile when the researchers listen to them, and there is the exact opposite. Music helps to learn: Many people who suffer from slow memorization can memorize songs, and this indicates that music helps them memorize and increases concentration, and it can be used to increase mind and thinking skills. As a result of knowing all these key points that music aids in treating, the researcher now knows the extent to which it is effective on the human mind and its behavior, and this past study finds that it is also effective on adolescents and in a significant and noticeable way. The researcher chose to

make it the focus of this study or the most critical point in this study. Which the researcher wants all teens to focus on completely and accurately.

Limitations and delimitations

According to a problem the researcher are facing, some parents are not taking mental illness as a serious problem that needs to be solved, they are not paying much attention to their teen's emotions and the effects of the situations they are going through on their mental health. Another problem is that a huge part of the community does not believe the fact that music can be a therapy that can help teens overcome their mental illness.

In this study, the researcher is trying to educate and spread awareness about this topic to help build up an educated community that stands beside teenagers and helps them overcome their mental illness using music therapy. The researcher would also like to help teenagers understand that they should not be ashamed to express their feelings and ask for help when needed. In this study, the researcher aims to help teenagers know the right way to react and deal with their emotions.

Independent Variable:

- Type of music whether it is instrumental, vocal, or acoustic.

Knowing the type of music, the teen usually listens to, the researcher can use music therapy to infer their psychological state. The type of music the teen listens to hugely contributes to how his/her psychological state will be. Different instruments will also have different effects on the patient's treatment lines. These details will all be carried out by the psychiatrist and will be highly confidential information.

Dependent Variables:

- How does the way music is expressed or received affect the psychological state of the teen?

The way they express music or receive it can hugely affect their psychological state. The way music might be received by the patient either by singing or just listening will highly contribute to the patient's psychological state.

- How music therapy could change the psychological state of the teen.

Let us say that a teen suffers from multiple psychological illnesses, with the help of music therapy, the teen will have a high chance of short-term recovery.

In this study the researcher claims to introduce an educated study stating advantages and disadvantages; however, emotional connections and effects on emotions is an aspect that will not be initiated in this study. This study is only based

on scientific searches and a well-educated thesis and information stated to us by this psychiatrist and the researchers researchers will be sharing it here. However, the emotional aspect of this study will not be tackled in this study.

Significance of the Study

In this study, the researcher is hoping to raise awareness toward this new field of therapy making it more common.

- Music therapy is not a common way of psychological therapy because of the lack of awareness about it. The goal of this study is to help raise awareness about it among teens.

This study will be well-proven by interviews with specialists well-addressed surveys and given assignments.

- The results of this study will be proven by well-known psychologists and specialized doctors in this field.

This study will add something new to the previously acquired studies.

This study will add awareness, and new information that other studies did not include. This mission here is to help other teens overcome psychological problems through a very helpful therapy called music therapy.

This study is handling the psychological effects of music on teens and how the various ways music can affect teens psychologically. This study is hoped to raise awareness, confidential hopes, and promising results to all readers and patients.

Definition of terms

Existentialism: a philosophical theory or approach that emphasizes the existence of the person as a free and responsible agent determining their development through acts of the will.

AMTA: “American Massage Therapy Association”; AMTA is the largest nonprofit community of massage therapists and the most respected name in the profession.

Adolescence: is a transitional stage of physical and psychological development that generally occurs during the period from puberty to adulthood.

Maladaptive behavior: is defined as behavior that interferes with an individual's activities of daily living or ability to adjust to and participate in particular settings.

Anesthesia: insensitivity to pain, especially as artificially induced by the administration of gases or the injection of drugs before surgical operations.

AIT: “Auditory Integration Training”; is a type of sound therapy, similar to the Tomatis method. It aims to reduce sensitivity to sounds or other problems with how sounds are processed.

Schizophrenia: a long-term mental disorder of a type involving a breakdown in the relation between thought, emotion, and behavior, leading to faulty perception, inappropriate actions and feelings, withdrawal from reality and personal relationships into fantasy and delusion, and a sense of mental fragmentation.

Autism: Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a neurological and developmental disorder that affects how people interact with others, communicate, learn, and behave. Although autism can be diagnosed at any age, it is described as a “developmental disorder” because symptoms generally appear in the first two years of life.

Insomnia: habitual sleeplessness; inability to sleep.

Dementia: is not a specific disease but is rather a general term for the impaired ability to remember, think, or make decisions that interfere with doing everyday activities. Alzheimer's disease is the most common type of dementia. Though dementia mostly affects older adults, it is not a part of normal aging.

Alzheimer's disease: is the most common type of dementia. It is a progressive disease beginning with mild memory loss and possibly leading to loss of the ability to carry on a conversation and respond to the environment. Alzheimer's disease involves parts of the brain that control thought, memory, and language.

CHAPTER II

Review of Related Literature

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework talks about what theories about music are, how they are made, how they are used, and how they help.

What does music theory mean?

Music therapy theory is the field of study that deals with how music works. It studies and tests the language and notation of music, and distinguishes the patterns that control the techniques of composers with remarkable sensitivity

Music theory is the study of the practices and possibilities of music. It is the field of study that deals with how music works. It studies and tests the language and notation of music, and distinguishes the patterns that control composers' techniques with an exceptional sensitivity. Music theory may include any statement, belief, or concept about music. People who study these properties are known as music theorists. Some apply acoustics, human physiology, and psychology to explain how and why music is a sensation.

It is quite challenging to understand the theory of music therapy. Because there are various ideas regarding the mechanisms of music as a therapeutic

method, the theory of music is a relatively empathetic field of study. Music therapy is an interdisciplinary field, and the area of music psychology is an innovative interdisciplinary science drawn from the fields of musicology, psychology, acoustics, sociology, anthropology, and neuroscience. Psychologists use experiments and diagnostics such as questionnaires and a perception model to analyze what is happening in music therapy.

Music therapy theory

One of the most common theories is the theory of music, mood, and movement (MMM) was developed from physical activity guidelines and music theory using the principles of statement and theory synthesis. The concepts of music, physical activity, and health outcomes were searched using the CINAHL, MEDLINE, ProQuest Nursing and Allied Health Source, PsycINFO, and Cochrane Library databases covering the years 1975-2008.

The theory of MMM was synthesized by combining the psychological and physiological responses of music to increase physical activity and improve health outcomes. It proposes that music alters mood, is a cue for movement, and makes physical activity more enjoyable. This leads to improved health outcomes for weight, blood pressure, blood sugar, and cardiovascular risk factor management, and improved quality of life.

Music theory is often concerned with describing how musicians and composers make music, including tuning systems and composition methods among other topics. Because of the ever-increasing conception of what constitutes music (see definition of music), a more inclusive definition could be that music theory is a consideration of any sound phenomena, including silence, as they relate to music. These are not absolute guidelines; For example, the study of "music" in the liberal arts college curriculum in the teachings (sciences) that was popular in medieval Europe was an abstract system of proportions carefully studied at a distance from current musical practice. However, in the Middle Ages, this discipline became the basis for tuning systems in later centuries and is generally included in modern studies on the history of music theory

Music theory as a practical discipline includes the methods and concepts that composers and other musicians use in creating music. The development, preservation, and transmission of music theory in this sense can be found in the traditions of oral and written music-making, musical instruments, and other works of art. For example, ancient tools from Mesopotamia and China and prehistoric sites around the world will reveal details about the music they produced and possibly something of a musical theory that may have been used by those makers (see History of Music and Musical Instruments). In ancient and living cultures around the world, the deep and long roots of music theory are visible in the

instruments, oral traditions, and the making of current music. Many cultures, at least as far back as ancient Mesopotamia and ancient China, have also looked at music theory in more formal ways such as written treatises and music. Practical and scholarly traditions overlap, as many of the practical treatises on music place themselves within the tradition of other treatises, what is cited by scholarly writing only cites earlier studies regularly.

In modern academia, music theory is a subfield of musicology, the broader study of musical cultures and histories. Fundamentally, music theory is the speculative work of music, in Greek theory, looking, seeing, contemplating, speculating, theory, also sight, spectacle. As such, it is often concerned with abstract musical aspects such as tuning, tonality, scales, harmony and dissonance, and rhythmic relations, but there is also a range of theories relating to practical aspects, such as the creation or performance of music, warping, embellishment, improvisation, and vocal production. mail. A person who researches, teaches, or writes articles about music theory is a music theorist. Undergraduate study, usually to MA or PhD level, is required to teach as a tenure-tracking theorist at a US or Canadian university. Methods of analysis include mathematics, graphic analysis, and the special analysis enabled by Western musical notation. Comparative, descriptive,

Music therapy as procedural support for invasive medical procedures:
toward the development of music therapy theory:

In partial response to the demand for evidence-based practice, there is increasing interest in the use of music therapy as procedural support for both invasive and non-invasive medical procedures. Clinicians and researchers are attempting to define how music therapy functions as procedural support. This is to advance clinical practice and study, but these concepts remain inadequately specified in the literature. The current philosophical inquiry used qualitative document analysis to critically examine the extant literature in music therapy as procedural support during invasive medical procedures. The analysis aimed to identify key concepts, provide definitions of those concepts, and begin to explicate the interrelationships among concepts related to music therapy as procedural support. A total of 19 clinical practice articles, clinical practice book chapters, and study articles met the criteria for inclusion in the analysis. Data analysis and synthesis resulted in a working model of music therapy as procedural support, in which the music therapist engages in a reflexive process of continually assessing the patient's responses to refocus the intervention lens (e.g., altering aspects of the music, of focus of attention, and patient/therapist interaction) to positively influence outcomes. It is hoped that the working model of music therapy as

procedural support may stimulate clinical dialogue. This may serve as an initial systematic step toward theory construction in this area.

Music therapy books

This is Your Brain on Music: The Science of a Human Obsession by Daniel J. Levitin, a neuroscientist, musician, and author, addresses questions such as:

- Are this musical preferences shaped in utero?
- Is there a cutoff point for acquiring new tastes in music?
- What do PET scans and MRIs reveal about the brain's response to music?
- Is musical pleasure different from other kinds of pleasure?

Ultimately, Levitin looks at how nature and nurture affect the human obsession that is music.

Music philia: Tales of Music and the Brain by Oliver Sacks, a physician, best-selling author, and Professor of Neurology at the NYU School of Medicine. He is known as the "poet laureate of medicine," according to The New York Times.

In Music Philia, Sacks looks at where music collides with the brain and how it affects the human condition. He does this by showing fascinating case studies,

or what he calls “musical misalignments.” These include stories of musically gifted people and those who cannot appreciate music in its entirety.

Touched with Fire: Manic-Depressive Illness and the Artistic Temperament by Kay Redfield Jamison, the Co-Director of the Mood Disorders Center and Professor of Psychiatry and Behavioral Sciences at John Hopkins Medicine.

In Touched with Fire, Jamison turns speculation into reality by exposing the links between manic depression and creativity. Manic and depressive states were once thought to accompany genius, but the researcher now know these are the signs of manic-depressive illnesses. Jamison analyzes artists such as Lord Byron, Vincent Van Gogh, and Virginia Woolf to better understand the underlying illnesses they may have harbored

How Music Works: The Science and Psychology of Beautiful Sounds, from Beethoven to the Beatles and Beyond by John Powell, best known as a Film Score Composer. He has worked on several popular movies like -- Solo: A Star Wars Story (2018), How to Train Your Dragon (2010), and Rio (2011).

Powell engages the reader with his entertaining descriptions of the scientific and psychological aspects of music. He includes animated discussions about timbre, harmony, keys, chords, composition, and anything else a musician wonders about -- well almost.

Music, the Brain and Ecstasy: How Music Captures This Imagination by Robert Jourdain, touches on several topics among science and technology while integrating his joy of playing the piano and composing.

For those who value entertainment while learning, Jourdain's Music, the Brain, and Ecstasy will not disappoint. He explores how music speaks when words fail and why it is so powerful while fascinating his audience with exotic characters.

The Music Instinct: How Music Works and Why The researchers Can't Do Without It by Philip Ball, a British Science Writer. Before going freelance, he worked at Nature for 20 years. Ball dives into questions such as:

- Why can music excite deep passions?
- How do the researchers make sense of musical sound?
- Why do all cultures seem to make music?

Using the latest study in music psychology and neuroscience, Ball explains how music seems to make its way into every aspect of life.

The Singing Neanderthals: The Origins of Music, Language, Mind, and Body by Steven Mithen, a Professor of Archeology at the University of Reading in the United Kingdom. In writing The Singing Neanderthals, he combines his knowledge with the properties of music.

Mithen introduces his theories and scientific data to support the notion that all humans share a musical and linguistic heritage. He focuses on the Neanderthals, their habits, and the mark they made on the world.

Tune In: A Music Therapy Approach to Life by Jennifer Buchanan, a Music Therapist, Author, Health Entrepreneur, and Speaker.

Buchanan's Tune In combines personal stories, case studies, exercises, and tips for those who want to improve their mood through music therapy.

Group Music Activities for Adults with Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities by Maria Ramey, a Flutist and Music Therapist who provides individual and group therapy for both children and adults.

Her 2011 book, Group Music Activities for Adults with Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities, was written with adult therapy in mind -- commonly group music activities are written for children. She includes 100 group music activities, each with clear instructions and a therapeutic goal behind it. Whether you are a music therapist, caregiver, or other professional working with adults, this book will inspire you to try new musical activities.

Music Therapy Handbook: Edited by Barbara L. Wheeler, who served as the past president of the American Music Therapy Association, and she has since accomplished great clinical and scholarly feats.

A more recent publication, 2015, Music Therapy Handbook gives its readers a complete overview of music therapy -- from basic concepts to clinical approaches. The book involves experts' opinions and study on the psychodynamic, humanistic, cognitive-behavioral, and developmental psychology of music. Other topics include music therapy's role in childhood development, autism spectrum disorder, brain injury, school interventions, and trauma.

Conceptual Framework:

A conceptual framework is a representation of the relationship you expect to see between your variables or the characteristics or properties that you want to study.

Conceptual frameworks can be written or visual and are generally developed based on a literature review of existing studies about your topic. These frameworks can then be used to guide your study and help you develop a better understanding of your study question.

The musical meaning since the 19th century

Before the 19th century, musicians themselves were not theorists, a theorist is defined as one who explicates meaning. Music theory, when it was something other than the exposition of a prevalent or emerging style, was likely to be a technical manual guiding vocal or instrumental performance, a set of directions for meeting current exigencies in church or theatre practice, or a missive advocating reforms. Prolific masters, such as Johann Sebastian Bach, produced not learned treatises but monuments to art.

According to Richard Wagner the 19th century saw the emergence of composer-critics (Carl Maria von Weber, Robert Schumann, Hector Berlioz, Franz Liszt), versatile artists with literary proclivities who were not, to be sure, propounding comprehensive theories or systems of thought. Richard Wagner, an active theorist, presaged the first species, the composer-author. But he did little to advance music theory. He proposed a unity of music and drama (Gesamtkunstwerk)—a reflection of the programmatic preoccupations of 19th-century composers—but its multiplicity of musical and extra-musical elements only added to the confusion of musical thought. The distinctly musical character of Wagner's genius, clearly discernible in *The Ring of the Nibelung* (*Der Ring des Nibelungen*), a set of four operas, is in no way explained by his discursive credo. Igor Stravinsky, Arnold Schoenberg, and other composers and authors of the 20th century were somewhat more successful in elucidating their techniques and aims.

Frequency Theory of Hearing

Wavelength is measured in frequency and amplitude. Frequency is measured in Hertz (Hz) which determines the pitch of a sound according to the length of the wave. The amplitude of a wave determines the loudness of a sound by looking at the height of a sound wave and is calculated in decibels (dB). The so-called normal range of hearing for a healthy young person is between 20 and 20,000Hz. In loudness, this ranges from 0 to 180 dB. However, anything over 85dB can cause damage to the human ear.

The frequency theory of hearing relies on looking at the frequency of a wave to determine its pitch. This allows the wavelength of sound vibrations to be replicated into electrical impulses to reach the auditory nerve. Once reaching the auditory nerve, the impulses are then signaled or in terms of this theory, copied, to the brain. When hearing a sound with a frequency of 100Hz, it is equivalent to 100 nerve impulses being transmitted per second by the auditory nerve. This theory falls short as a neuron cannot fire at a rate that is larger than 500 impulses per second, thus would only account for lower pitch sounds. The higher-pitched sounds, according to this theory, would not be heard because a single neuron cannot fire at a fast enough rate.

A frequency theory explains that the same amount of nerve impulses are sent to the brain each time a sound is heard. When an individual hears a frequency of 100Hz, the equivalent of 100 impulses per second is then transmitted via the auditory nerve to the brain. This theory falls short as a neuron has a refractory period which does not allow a neuron to fire faster than 500 impulses per second. This is because the human ear can perceive frequencies much louder than 500Hz.

Theory of Sound Waves and Collective Description

The linearized equation of the density matrix is applied to generalize the theory of sound waves due to Bloch and Tomonaga. It has been shown that the true scattering matrix is given by the Hamiltonian oscillator obtained by this method. The generalized theory of sound waves, which may be considered as a generalized Hartree approximation, is not only capable of yielding the correct plasma frequency and the screening interaction of metallic ions but also facilitates the analysis of higher-order perturbations. The relationship to Bohm and Pines' collective description is pointed out and a polarization field is introduced in place of the longitudinal electric field. As an example, the researchers consider the electron-lattice interaction, and it has been shown that the stability of the atomic lattice increases under the influence of Coulomb interaction. The limit of the

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applicability of this method is examined by the theory of transformation functions.

In the Appendix, the correlation energies of some alkali metals are obtained.

The tempo theory

Getting the tempo right to trigger an emotion may not be a part of the songwriting you considered before. But finding the right tempo can undoubtedly make a difference. Study shows that “music with a fast tempo has been found to evoke positive emotions, such as happiness, excitement, delight, and liveliness, while music with a slow tempo evokes negative emotions, such as sadness, depression, and gravity.” (Peretz et al., 1998; Balkwill and Thompson, 1999; Juslin and Sloboda, 2001). One of the reasons why the researchers say that something is “upbeat” when it’s happy and positive, or “downbeat” when it’s sad or depressing.

It’s interesting to play with the tempo of your song. Changing it can give a different vibe, affecting the impact of the song or even its message. You often experience this during live concerts, when the artist or band plays it slightly faster compared to the studio version, giving it a different feel for the occasion.

The fact that the researcher reacts to tempo is because the tempo of music has a direct effect on this heart rate. The heart’s rhythm aims to sync with the music and is therefore influenced by it. That also means that the tempo of a song roughly equates with the heartbeat that is associated with the emotion that the music

suggests. Whenever the researcher experienced excitement or anxiety, his heartbeat rises. This also means that when this heartbeat increases because of the music that the researcher is exposed to, the researcher experience similar inner emotions; in this case, excitement or anxiety.

In general, a fast pace causes enthusiasm, joy, and anger, while a slow pace triggers feelings of relaxation or depression. Below is a simple overview of tempo (expressed in beats per minute) and the emotional feeling they convey:

- 60 BPM is often relaxing, introspective, or even depressive, but also with love and less drama.
- 80-100 BPM (think heartbeat speed) is moderately alert and engaging, accompanied by feelings of fulfillment, rewarding, and sometimes relaxing too.
- 100+ BPM is considered lively, exciting, or agitating, a feeling of power.
- Typical heart rates range from 120 to 185 beats per minute. This includes high-energy situations, feelings of excitement, anger, or drama.

So, what makes, for instance, a slow beat calm and relaxed or depressive, which are two extreme ends of the emotional spectrum? That seems to be related

to the combination of the mode or key and the tempo of the song. There has been extensive study into this matter. The overview below shows a variety of emotions most frequently chosen by musicians and nonmusicians while listening to three pieces in different modes and tempi.

Theories of emotion in music and their implications for study in music psychology:

Work in musical aesthetics on musical meaning is relevant to psychological study into musical expressions of emotion. Distinctions between simple emotions, high emotions, and moods are given, and arguments as to what kinds of emotions or moods music might be able to express (given music's semantic capacities and limitations) are summarized. Next, the question of how music might express these emotions and moods is considered. The paper concludes with several cautionary points for researchers in the psychology of music emotion: musical expression always involves sonic properties, which must be taken into account. If one uses "real world" musical stimuli, one may be faced with associative interference. The context will often individuate emotional expression, transforming a simple emotion into a higher emotion by providing an intentional object. There is not a simple linear relationship between the intensity of a music parameter and the intensity of an emotional expression. Some perfectly good musical expressions of emotion may

not arouse those emotions in the listener, yet it would be incorrect to call such passages "inexpressive." Any emotions aroused by listening to music, while similar to emotions that occur in non-musical contexts, will nonetheless have several important differences. Therefore, it is important to recognize that the feelings communicated by music are distinct from those experienced in everyday life, and should not be judged by the same criteria

Foreign Literature

Based on the article published by the NIH (National Library of Medicine) in the United States, the development of music-based therapeutic services in the healthcare industry is being driven by the literature's growing body of evidence regarding the advantages of musical activities and music therapy. Music can be an excellent therapeutic option that is ideal for every setting and people of every age, ethnicity, and ethnic background because it promotes both physical and psychological health.

The autonomic nervous system's involvement in musical activities, music's potential inclusion as a component of an "enriched environment," and finally the positive effects of rhythmical movements and physical musical activities, and how they affect people's preferences for treatment options, are some aspects of music that this mini-review has not fully addressed because it is a complex topic.

Based on an article published by Lia Peralta on May 3, 2022, it cannot be denied that music has a significant psychological effect. A person's mood can be greatly affected by the music they listen to, which can also help them process a wide range of emotions by allowing them to go deeper into their consciousness. And it's not simply that music stirs up emotions; there is evidence to back up the impact music has on us.

The processing and generation of music for mental health differs from that of spoken language. Patients who can communicate without using words can express themselves more freely, connect with their loved ones on a deeper level, and feel more secure in their identity. Patients who have undergone trauma, for instance, frequently struggle to express their emotions or describe the specific incident (s). They can articulate their challenges with the use of music therapy, particularly the lyrical component of music. Lyrics are an "easier entryway for expression" than spoken words, according to one music therapist.

Local Studies

According to an experimental study done by Saudi musician Abdullah Khoja in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, throughout middle school, Khoja found that he liked playing the piano and guitar, which helped him feel better.

Then, he started playing the guitar and joined a band. He participated in numerous activities and gave performances in eateries in Jeddah with his bandmates.

As Khoja claims to himself: "It's like talking to someone," Khoja said. "I wasn't good at expressing my feelings, so I channeled this energy through music and found my passion for piano and guitar the most. I play the piano when I am depressed, and I play the guitar when I'm angry."

Also, according to a study by college researchers, one of the earliest methods of healing that humans have used to enhance their health is sound healing. This therapy uses music, vibrations, and spoken tones to improve both physical and mental well-being.

It is based on a variety of musical elements, and because different harmonic vibrations have a significant impact, using them to improve one's physical or mental health can be quite beneficial. Finding a useful use for instruments like singing bowls, Shruti boxes, gongs, Tingsha bells, monochords, didgeridoos, and alchemical crystal bowls is the crux of this discipline. Chanting and nature noises are both included in the broad definition of sound therapy. It is also linked to emotional reactions that alter one's physical and mental well-being and encourage

harmony or balance between the two. Inducing serenity and reducing memory obstruction at the cellular level are all things that sound waves do to the brain.

Local Literature

Summarized from the book of Sarah Muhsin Al-Hamdan, The Healing Process of Music Therapy, "The systematic process of intervention wherein the Therapist assists the Client in promoting Health, using Music Experiences and the Relationships that form through them as Dynamic Forces of Change," is how music therapy is defined.

Three music therapy techniques are employed as main interventions:

- Improvisatory, which can be performed vocally or instrumentally and can be done solo or in collaboration with a group.
- Re-creative activities include song analysis and debate, as well as music-supported art forms like music and art encounters or music interventions in movements.
- Receptive is the term for an individual or stylized group vocal or instrumental rendition of a favorite song, also referred to as a song re-creation.

Synthesis and Relevance of Studies

Both the local and foreign studies and literature presented above agreed to one similar point: music therapy is not just a typical therapy that would be with minimal help to being completely useless: furthermore, music therapy is considered one of the most reliable and easier therapies nowadays. Despite minimal disadvantages, music therapy is the future therapy for all psychological issues. Some of the music therapy disadvantages are Overstimulation - There are a lot of factors in regards to the sound behind the music. Memory Triggering - Music is second only to smell in its ability to incite unwanted memories and Anxiety.

Despite that, music therapy has a lot of advantages which can be split into psychological advantages, emotional advantages, or improving lifestyles. This study is mostly focused on the psychological aspect. Music therapy aids us to be calm, productive, and enduring all problems. It also helps in aiding a bad day or a bad mood by improving the psychological aspect.

To be exact, the part of the brain that governs movement is quickly activated when you listen to music. For example, when your favorite song starts playing and you feel the want to get up and move, the music is working. Using music therapy to relieve stress is healthy. While tougher genres can help you release some stored

frustration, calming tunes can help you slow down you're thinking. Also, music has a significant impact on your mental wellness.

These studies mostly target teenagers, which makes sense given that they make up the majority of the population. Teenagers are the age group in which human goes through the hardest situations and life experiences. Therapy would help teens to relieve their stress and live a better positive life during this period of their lives.

In the following parts of this study, these papers and information collected from both local and foreign sources will be used to find advantages, usages, and concerns regarding music therapy for teenagers.

Chapter III

Methodology

Method of Study

This study aims to inform and educate the teenagers of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia about the psychological effects of music therapy on teenagers of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. This study will also raise awareness of music therapy in a wide range. This study will later be published to a wider range in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia to teach and educate everyone not just teenagers on music therapy.

The Subject of the Study

The targeted subjects of this study are teenagers from the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. To keep through this study, the study education population is not only limited to the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia but on a wider range globally. As mentioned previously in Chapter I, Statement of the Problem, the main problem that the researchers faced in this study was that the teenagers were not well educated about the psychological effects of music on their psychological state. Also, it was quite difficult for the team to find a specific psychologist who specialized in the therapeutic of teenagers. This problem was solved later after the team did a consecutive search across Riyadh, Saudi Arabia for a specialized

psychologist to conduct interviews with, and later the psychologist provided questions on the survey questionnaire to publish across Saudi Arabia.

Description of Study Instrument

The instrument used to gather respondents' answers is a survey questionnaire prepared using Google form and distributed via WhatsApp and other social media websites. The questionnaire consisted of 15 questions which consisted of close-ended questions to evaluate the following of the teenagers:

- The current psychological state of the teenager while answering the survey.
- The social state of the teenager.
- How does the teenager take care of their psychological state?
- The correlation between music and their mood.
- The popularity of music therapy in their lives.

The questionnaire included close-ended questions to provide short, assured answers to the mentioned criteria above. Close-ended questions helped in providing definite answers to the questions asked by the psychologists.

Data Gathering Procedure

There are three sources for the data in this study: interviews with specialists of psychological effects of music and therapeutic specialists, related literature and studies done previously on this aspect (which were discussed in the previous chapter), and the survey's questionnaire responses. The interviews helped in meeting with the proficient psychologists which provided the team with first-hand information. The responses to the questionnaires helped the team to gather accurate percentages on different aspects and effects of the study that were mentioned previously.

The study design used in this study is a qualitative-quantitative method since it collects data about the respondent's previous psychological state moving through their current state, how might music affect their mood and do they consider using music as a therapeutic method later on if they ever faced a psychological matter. The study also uses quantitative methods since statistical data will be counted from the questionnaire and transformed them into factual percentages that will be published later on if it was possible.

The data was gathered from teenagers around the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The survey was shared with them by friends, families, and other social relatives through Via WhatsApp and other social media platforms. About 100

respondents were required to construct a fair data generalization. But, since some respondents' answers were invalid, I had to allow more than 100 respondents to gather the most valid 100 responses out of them. 126 responses were gathered.

Statistical Data Applied

Graphs and tables will be included for each of the fifteen questions of the survey questionnaire. As for the conclusion, through Chapter V, a detailed summary of the whole study findings will be attached and a thorough summary of the whole study criteria will also be provided for a clearer view of the study. Relation between the study aspects will also be provided as part of the conclusion. For example, the relation between appetite and the psychological state, or the relation between music and how it affects the mood of the respondent...etc. All these aspects and relations will be provided through statistical graphs and tables in the final Chapter of this study.

Chapter IV

Results and Discussion

This study has been widely disseminated throughout the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia and specifically for the population of Riyadh (teenagers) aged 13 to 19 years. The target number was 100 respondents, and the researchers obtained 141 responses. If there are any errors or invalid answers from the additional 40 people, the number will be reduced to 100 people. Of the 141 people, the target group (teenagers) aged 13 to 19 was only 101 people, so the researchers deleted the rest because they were not of any importance in this study. This means the following results to be discussed are based on the responses of 101 respondents which all are (teenagers).

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According to the graphs above, the largest proportion of this participants' ages was the teenager's group. The researcher originally had 141 responses to the survey and the teenager's group was (101) out of 141, which makes it excellent for this study because here, the researcher is targeting teens only and any age under 13 and above 19 has been removed from the study. As the figure above shows, 20% of the participants were children (7-12 years old), all of whom were primary school students. 8% (the smallest category) of participants were adults (20-40+ years), this largest age group and most of them are college or university students or Recent graduates and others have jobs and families. (This age group is not needed or related to this study). Finally, 72%, the highest percentage of participants, are teenagers (age 13-19) (the ideal age group for this study) who are middle and high school students.

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1) Are you happy or in a good mood while answering the questions?

101 responses

According to the above graph, 51% (the largest category) of the participants are in a happy and good mood while answering the questions while 37% are not sure whether they are having a good time or in a good mood while answering the questions. and 12% (the smallest category) of the respondents are not happy and in a bad mood while answering the questions.

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According to the graph above, 33% of the respondents are enjoying their time, while 56% (the largest category) of the respondents are not sure if they are having a good time. and 11% (the smallest category) of the respondents are not enjoying their time at all.

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According to the graph above, 14% (the smallest category) of the respondents always sleep well and don't have any problems, while 21% of the respondents don't sleep well and have a very bad and messy sleep. And 65% (the largest category) of the respondents said they sometimes feel like both.

According to the graph above, 54% (the largest category) of the respondents have a moderate appetite for food and they eat, but not everything, while 37% of the respondents have a good appetite and they eat almost everything. And 9% (the smallest category) of the respondents have a very low appetite and don't eat at all.

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According to the graph above, 35% of the respondents socialize with other people, while 59% (the largest category) don't socialize as much with others. And 6% (the smallest category) of the respondents don't socialize with people.

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According to the graph above, 34% (the largest category) of the sample began to socialize with others in grades (10-12), who are high school students, while 20% (the smallest category) of the respondents began to socialize with others in grades (1-3) and (4-6) who are primary school students. Finally, 26% of the respondents began to socialize with others in grades (7-9), which are middle school students.

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7) Do you take care of yourself and your mental or physical health?

101 responses

According to the graph above, 49% (the largest category) of the respondents take care of themselves and their mental and physical health a little while 42% of the respondents do take care of themselves very well. and 9% (the smallest category) of the respondents don't take care of their mental and physical health.

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According to the graph above, 49% (the largest category) of respondents feel that they are sometimes motivated to work in their daily activities and have some goals in life, while 38% of respondents feel that they are motivated to work well in their daily activities and have goals for their future, and 13% (the smallest category) Of the respondents they have no motivation to work in their daily activities and have no goals in life at all.

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9) Do you suffer from any mental illnesses or have you had them before? (eg:

101 responses

According to the graph above, 32% of the respondents have mental illnesses or had them before, while 35% (the largest category) of the respondents are well and don't have any mental illnesses and never had them before. And 33% (the smallest category) of the respondents were not sure if they had or hadn't had any mental illnesses before.

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According to the graph above, 72% (the largest category) of the respondents agreed that music has affected their mood before, while 18% agreed that music sometimes affects their mood. and 10% (the smallest category) agreed that music doesn't affect their mood at all.

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11) Have you heard about music therapy before?

According to the graph above, 44% (the largest category) of the respondents have heard about music therapy before, while 32% never heard of music therapy before. and 24% (the smallest category) were not sure whether they heard of music therapy before or didn't.

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According to the graph above, 73% (the largest category) of the respondents agreed that music can control their psychological state or mood while 12% think that music is not capable of controlling their psychological state or mood. and 15% (the smallest category) were not sure of its effects on their psychological state or their mood.

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13) Have you ever used music therapy before?

According to the graph above, 56% (the largest category) of the respondents have not tried music therapy before, while 44% (the smallest category) of the respondents did try music therapy before.

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According to the graph above, 84% (the largest category) of the respondents agreed to try music therapy because of their limited knowledge about it, while 16% (the smallest category) disagreed and will not try music therapy at all.

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15) If you feel sad or depressed, will you listen to music to make you feel better?

101 responses

According to the graph above, 60% (the largest category) of the respondents would listen to music when they feel sad or depressed to feel better, while 16% (the smallest category) would not listen to music at all if they feel sad or depressed. And 24% of the respondents responded with maybe.

Chapter V

Summary of Findings, Conclusions, and Recommendations

Summary

Based on the results in Chapter 4, the findings consistently demonstrate that music therapy offers a holistic approach to supporting the psychological well-being of teenagers. Most teenagers use music therapy to enhance their emotional state whether they are aware of the concept of music therapy or not. It allows them to explore and express their personal identity and fosters relaxation and a positive mood.

Conclusions

In conclusion, music therapy positively impacts the emotional well-being of teenagers by enhancing emotional regulation skills. It promotes relaxation and a positive mood, contributing to their overall emotional health. music therapy promotes social interaction and communication skills, leading to the formation of meaningful connections and improving their overall social well-being. Therefore, music therapy stands as a valuable therapeutic intervention that can significantly benefit the psychological health and development of teenagers.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study on the psychological effects of music therapy on teenagers, the following recommendations can be made:

1. Enhanced knowledge and instruction: Parents, teachers, and medical professionals should be more knowledgeable about the advantages of music therapy for teenagers. This can be addressed through education and training programs that stress the value and effectiveness of music therapy.
2. Increased awareness and education: To provide teenagers with this helpful intervention, music therapy programs ought to be incorporated into school curricula. Teenagers can regularly experience the healing effects of music by integrating music therapy into educational settings.
3. Study and assessment: More investigation is required to determine the precise mechanisms and long-term impacts of music therapy on teenagers. Continuous program assessment in music therapy can yield data-driven insights and aid in the creation of evidence-based procedures.
4. Personalized approach: Recognizing individual differences and preferences, music therapy should be tailored to each teenager's needs and interests. By

incorporating their musical preferences and strengths, the effectiveness of music therapy can be maximized.

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Appendices

Appendix A

Survey Questionnaire

Introduction

This study aims to inform people about the psychological effects of music therapy and to help people whose lives have been affected by injury, illness, or disability by supporting their psychological, emotional, cognitive, physical, communicative, and social needs among a wide age group in Riyadh, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia and provide the possible causes, effects, and solution to problems. By answering this survey, you will help us reach this aim.

Disclaimer: Be fully assured that your response is of high confidentiality and is only open to the study team.

Name:

Nationality:

Age:

Direction:

There are no right or wrong answers. Kindly, answer the following questions honestly. Choose the answer to the best of your knowledge.

1) Are you happy or in a good mood while answering the questions?

- a) Yes
- b) No
- c) Maybe

2) Are you enjoying your time?

- a) yes
- b) a little
- c) not at all

3) Do you always sleep well?

- a) Yes
- b) Sometimes
- c) No, my sleep is bad and messy

4) How is your appetite for food?

- a) Good, I eat almost everything
- b) I eat but not everything
- c) Bad, I can't eat at all

5) Do you like to socialize with different people?

- a) Yes
- b) Not so much
- c) No

6) Since when did you like to socialize?

- a) 1-3 Grade
- b) 4-6 Grade
- c) 7-9 Grade
- d) 10-12 Grade

7) Do you take care of yourself and your mental or physical health?

- a) Yes
- b) A little
- c) No

8) Do you have goals or motivation to work on your daily activities?

- a) Yes
- b) Sometimes
- c) No

9) Do you suffer from any mental illnesses or have you had them before?

(eg: depression, anxiety, etc.)

- a) Yes
- b) No
- c) I'm not sure

10) Has music ever affected your mood?

- a) Yes
- b) Sometimes
- c) No

11) Have you heard about music therapy before?

- a) Yes
- b) I'm not sure
- c) No

12) Do you think music can control your psychological / mood state?

- a) Yes
- b) No
- c) I'm not sure

13) Have you ever used music therapy before?

- a) Yes
- b) No

14) If you haven't, tried music therapy, would you like to try it?

- a) Yes
- b) No

15) If you feel sad or depressed, will you listen to music to make you feel better?

- a) Yes
- b) No
- c) Maybe

